

$$\begin{aligned} x' &= a_0 + a_1x + a_2y + a_3xy \\ y' &= b_0 + b_1x + b_2y + b_3xy, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

to convert the tip position on the image into the desirable cursor position on the screen, because this distortion could not be taken into consideration well enough. As the result, the error would occur in the estimated cursor position.

To show the above-mentioned error, the virtual touch screen using camera shown in Fig. 1 is set up in the simulation. The eye and the pin-hole camera are located at the same height as the height of the screen center. The focal length of the camera is 6.2 mm.

Fig. 2 shows the simulation result of the screen with 289 markers positioning at (x, y) when $x, y = 25*i$ and $i = 0, 1, \dots, 16$.

Fig. 2 Simulation result of the screen with 289 markers.

Under the system environment shown in Fig.1, if the user points the indicator tip on the screen cover so that the tip is located on each marker when it has been looked from the eye position, each indicator tip position on the image taken from the camera would be as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Simulation result of each indicator tip position on the image taken from the camera.

Fig. 4 shows the simulation result of image-screen mapping using bilinear transformation with 4 couples (pairs of the image coordinates of indicator tip and the screen coordinates of desirable cursor) of corresponding known points (called "tie points") positioning at the 4 corners of the screen.

Fig. 4 Simulation result of image-screen mapping using bilinear transformation (whole image).

The desirable cursor is shown with x mark, and the estimated cursor is shown with + mark.

From Fig. 4, the error becomes larger when the indicator moves toward the left of the screen. One way to reduce the error is partitioning an image into smaller subimages and applying the bilinear transformation to each subimage.

Fig. 5 shows the simulation result of partitioning an image into smaller rectangular subimages, and for each subimage, applying image-screen mapping using bilinear transformation with 4 couples of tie points at the corner of each subimage.

Fig. 5 Simulation result of image-screen mapping using bilinear transformation (subimage).

The desirable cursor is shown with x mark, and the estimated cursor is shown with + mark.

From Fig. 5, even though the bilinear transformation is applied to each subimage, the error is still visible in each

subimage. The reason is that the degrees of polynomial equations in the bilinear transformations are not high enough to imitate the distortion occurring during image-screen mapping. In theory, if the higher degree of polynomial equation is applied to image-screen mapping, the error would become smaller. But increasing the degree of polynomial equation requires more known tie points. For example, if

$$\begin{aligned} x' &= a_0 + a_1x + a_2y + a_3xy + a_4x^2 + a_5y^2 + a_6x^2y + a_7xy^2 + a_8x^2y^2 \\ y' &= b_0 + b_1x + b_2y + b_3xy + b_4x^2 + b_5y^2 + b_6x^2y + b_7xy^2 + b_8x^2y^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

are used in the image-screen mapping, the user must provide 8 couples of corresponding known points. This could be done by asking the user to point the indicator tip at 8 on-screen markers, taking a picture for each time, and then keep the positions of each pair of coordinates, i.e., image coordinates of the tip and screen coordinates of the marker. If the system requires more accuracy, then higher degree of polynomial equation must be employed, such as the following general polynomial equation:

$$\begin{aligned} x' &= \sum_{r=0}^m \sum_{k=0}^{m-r} a_{rk} x^r y^k \\ y' &= \sum_{r=0}^m \sum_{k=0}^{m-r} b_{rk} x^r y^k. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

This means that the user must help the system to locate more couples of tie points. As the result, the user might feel inconvenient.

In the next section, more efficacious and error-free mapping algorithm is proposed to solve these problems.

III. THE PROPOSED MODEL

Cursor position estimation model for virtual touch screen using camera is proposed in this paper. The proposed model allow the camera to be positioned anywhere that the whole screen can be captured into an image, i.e., the camera could be positioned more than 30 degrees off of the normal line. This means that the home users need not to use the wearable camera, but they just put their ordinary webcam anywhere on the desk where the whole screen could be captured. Furthermore the gap between the screen and the screen cover could be any length, i.e., the screen could be an LCD or an ordinary monitor. The proposed model is capable of eliminating the distortion error in a previous image-screen mapping method. The proposed algorithm is described as follows.

A. Configuration for pilot cursor to desirable cursor mapping

For the first time of use, user must provide 4 couples of *pilot cursor* positions and *desirable cursor* positions. The pilot cursor is the cursor positioning on the screen just behind the indicator tip when they are viewed from the camera. The desirable cursor is the cursor positioning on the screen just behind the indicator tip when they are viewed from the user's eye. These 4 couples of coordinates will be used later to map the other pilot cursor positions to the desirable cursor positions during the use of virtual touch screen system. The detailed algorithm is described as follows.

Step A1: Display the desirable cursor on the screen.

Step A2: Put the indicator on the screen cover so that the indicator tip is just over the desirable cursor when they are viewed from the user's eye.

Step A3: Move the pilot cursor on the screen toward the position of the indicator tip until the pilot cursor is just behind the indicator tip when they are viewed from the camera (i.e., until the image coordinates of the pilot cursor equal to the image coordinates of the indicator's tip).

Step A4: Keep the positions of the pilot cursor and the corresponding desirable cursor.

Step A5: Display the next desirable cursor on the screen, and repeat step A2 – A4 until 4 couples of pilot cursors and desirable cursors are established.

Step A6: Use these 4 couples of coordinates and (1) to calculate the coefficients $a_0 - a_3$ and $b_0 - b_3$.

Step A7: Use the coefficients $a_0 - a_3$ and $b_0 - b_3$ from step A6 to establish the bilinear transformations which will be used in the next subsection.

B. Image-screen mapping using pilot cursor

To prevent the distortion from using the bilinear transformations in image-screen mapping during the execution of the virtual touch screen using camera, the pilot cursor created by the system is used instead to find the on-screen position which is just behind the indicator tip when they are viewed from the camera. This pilot cursor position will be used later to find the desirable cursor position. The detailed algorithm when user moves the indicator to the next position is described as follows.

Step B1: Segment the indicator from the image background.

Step B2: Find the tip position of the indicator on the current frame and compare it with the pilot cursor position on the last detectable frame. Determine the next moving direction by setting it to the vector from the pilot cursor position to the tip position.

Step B3: Move the pilot cursor on the screen toward the position of the indicator by some distance value. Keep its screen coordinates.

Step B4: Convert the screen coordinates of the pilot cursor to the screen coordinates of the desirable cursor by using bilinear transformations established in step A7.

Step B5: Segment the pilot cursor from the image background and keep its image coordinates.

Step B6: Repeat step B1 – B5 until, in the image, the pilot cursor locates at the same position as the indicator tip (i.e., when the pilot cursor is viewed from the camera, it locates just behind the indicator tip).

As described above, the mapping from the image coordinates of an indicator tip to the screen coordinates of a pilot cursor in step B1 – B3 and B5 – B6 is done by the help of the computer interactions, not by the bilinear transformations, thus it is guaranteed that there is no distortion occurred.

In addition, the conversion from the pilot cursor position to the desirable cursor position in step B4 is done between two

positions on the screen, so the normal bilinear transformation is adequate to be applied without any distortion.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The system environment used in the simulations is shown in Fig. 1. In the simulations, the screen is of size 400 mm × 400 mm, the interval between the screen and the screen cover is 5 mm, the user's eye locates at 400 mm away from the center of the screen cover and along the screen normal line, and the camera's pin hole locates at the same height as the eye, 200 mm in front of the screen cover, and 250 mm left of the screen normal line. The focal length of the camera is 6.2 mm.

In the simulations, the test pattern with 289 desirable cursor positions in Fig. 2 is used.

Fig. 6 Simulation result of pilot cursor positions (+ mark) comparing to desirable cursor positions (x mark).

Fig. 7 Simulation result of estimated cursor positions (+ mark) comparing to desirable cursor positions (x mark).

Fig. 6 shows the simulation result of pilot cursor positions (+ mark) when the aforementioned algorithm is applied. The desirable cursor positions (x mark) are also displayed for comparison.

Fig. 7 shows the simulation result of estimated cursor positions (+ mark) when the algorithm in step B4 is applied. The desirable cursor positions (x mark) are also displayed for comparison.

From Fig. 7, the estimated cursors locate exactly the same position as the desirable cursors. This means that if the pilot cursor position on the screen could be determined correctly by using the computer interaction described above, the desirable cursor position would be estimated correctly.

V. CONCLUSION

Cursor position estimation model for virtual touch screen using camera is proposed in this paper. The simulations show the efficiency and correctness of the proposed model. In the real world, there are still some issues to be solved, e.g., how far the moved distance value of the pilot cursor and which direction should be in step B3, what kind of the pilot cursor should be used to prevent the occlusion when the indicator moves over the pilot cursor, which condition should be used in step B6 to test whether the image coordinates of the pilot cursor are at the same position as the image coordinates of the indicator tip.

For the first issue, the moved distance of the pilot cursor could be set depending on the need of the user. If the user wants to simulate the rapid movement of the cursor, the value should be large; if not, the value should be small. In addition, the moved distance in the right area of the screen should be larger than the moved distance in the left area. If the camera is set as shown in Fig. 1, the pilot cursor could move in the screen in the same direction as the next moving direction determined in step B2.

For the second issue, the horizontal line which is longer than the horizontal length of the indicator could be used to prevent the occlusion.

For the third issue, if the horizontal line is used as the pilot cursor, it is easy to test whether the condition is true or false by testing the equality of the row position of the horizontal line and that of the indicator, and testing the equality of the column position of the horizontal line's midpoint and that of the indicator.

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